

D3.2– Catalogue of universal key genes responsible for oil yield and quality

Due date of deliverable: M42

Actual submission date: M52

Lead beneficiary

Wageningen University, Netherlands

Responsible Author

E.M.J. Salentijn WR

Additional Authors

Robert van Loo WR

Type

R	Document, report	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	<input type="checkbox"/>
DEC	Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
OTHER		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 727698.

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the Research Executive Agency (REA) or the European Commission (EC). REA or the EC are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Introduction

Plant oil biosynthesis is a complex process that is controlled by many enzymes and transcription factors and before the oil is formed, a complex network of biosynthetic pathways has been followed. In the model plant *Arabidopsis*, at least 120 enzymatic reactions and more than 600 genes encoding enzymes and regulatory factors are involved in the acyl-lipid metabolism (Li-Beisson et al. 2013). It is therefore a challenging task to choose appropriate target genes for developing EMS mutants with a desired oil yield and quality for crop improvement (e.g. Yuan and Li, 2020).

Within the framework of MAGIC, a catalogue of universal key genes responsible for oil quality is constructed. The database was created by selecting genes involved in oil-biosynthesis that are functionally conserved in multiple crops. This catalogue can be used to select the most promising target genes for breeding of oil/specialty crops using mutation breeding (D3-4) by showing pathway functionality of genes in both, model species and several oil crops (*Brassica napus*, *Camelina sativa*, *Crambe abyssinica* and *Glycine max*). The catalogue is publicly available as a supplementary xlsx file, accessible via <https://figshare.com/s/d5a4170f6046e00790d0> (DOI:10.4121/19411331)

Catalogue of universal key genes responsible for oil yield and quality

The catalogue presents currently identified structural genes acting in the fatty acid biosynthesis pathway and related pathways, from the model plant *Arabidopsis thaliana* and several oil crops (*Crambe abyssinica*, *Camelina sativa*, *Brassica napus*, soybean), together with the description of the enzyme they encode for and accession number to find more information on the genes. In the catalogue (sheet: catalogue of pathway genes), based on the **gene description** or **functional identifier** (KEGG orthology number; [KEGG: Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes](http://www.genome.jp/kegg/)) functional orthologs in other crops can be filtered (apply excel filter in the header row) and one can study the different pathways where the gene is active (pathway identifiers MAP, MAP2, pathway name). In another sheet (sheet: transcription factor) transcription factors that regulate the flux through the pathway are presented. Furthermore, genes are organized based on their annotation in the **Gene ontology database** (GO identifiers). A GO annotation gives actual information about the predicted function of particular genes. For instance, GO:0015908= genes involved in "fatty acid transport". In sheet "GO_fatty acid_crambe" the *Crambe abyssinica* genes annotated for a function related to fatty acids are presented. The genes from *Crambe abyssinica* are not yet available in the public domain and are therefore listed separate. This sheet contains also links to all other genes annotated for these GO terms. By clicking on the link and enter the taxon identifier in the taxon button on the "QuickGO" website, one can obtain the list of relevant genes for other taxons, i.e. camelina (taxon identifier no. mentioned in the .xlsx sheet). In the sheets "GO_seed oilbody biogenesis" and "GO_diacylglycerol biosynthesis" genes annotated for these functions are listed for the five species of this catalogue. In sheet "GO terms oil" relevant GO-terms for oil are given together with their hierarchical relation to GOs for other functions and processes.

Short introduction in oil biosynthesis

Fatty acids (FAs) in the form of lipids are found in three main regions of the plant cell:

- 1) surface lipids in the extra-cellular domains (wax, cuticle, suberin) derived from very long chain fatty acids (VLCFSAs);
- 2) phospholipids in cellular membranes (phosphatidylcholine, PC);
- 3) storage lipids in oil bodies (mainly triacylglycerol, TAG);
- 4) free fatty acids in the cytoplasm in the form of acyl-CoA.

This last source, the free acyl-CoA pool in the cytoplasm, delivers the FA substrates for **seed oil** (TAG) biosynthesis. This source of FAs originates from de novo fatty acid biosynthesis in the

chloroplast, and from membrane bound fatty acids (PC-FA) that are removed from the PC via a process termed 'acyl editing'. The actual TAG synthesis takes place in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) where the FAs from the **free acyl-CoA pool** are subjected to the action of the acyltransferases of the '**Kennedy pathway**' to form diacylglycerol (DAG) and thereafter TAG. DAG can also be produced by **direct exchange between membrane bound FAs** (PC-FA) and DAG, without the action of the 'Kennedy pathway' (via a PC-FA to DAG conversion (termed "head group exchange) and via transfer of the FA on position sn-2 of the PC-FA to the sn-3 of DAG). In the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and in the plastid also several fatty acid modifying enzymes are active such as desaturases that can add double bonds to the C18:1 (oleic acid) FA molecule, to produce polyunsaturated fatty acids, C18:2 (linoleic acid) and C18:3 (linolenic acid). The FAs can also be subjected to the action the endogenous FAE elongase system to generate very long chain fatty acids (VLCFAs), wax esters or ketone biosynthesis. When the plant needs more energy, the energy stored in fats/oils is released as ATP via the citric acid cycle through the β -oxidation of acetyl-CoA from the fats.

Overview of key genes involved in fatty acid biosynthesis

A. Key genes involved in plastidial "de novo" FA biosynthesis

The initial "de novo" biosynthesis of fatty acid from acetyl-CoA and NADPH takes place in the chloroplast. Most of the acetyl-CoA in the chloroplast is derived from carbohydrates via the glycolytic pathway. This pathway also provides the glycerol backbone for TAG. The plastidial fatty acid synthesis pathway determines the chain length (16 to 18 carbons) and the level of saturated fatty acids in the TAGs in seed oils.

A1. Plastidial acetyl CoA carboxylase (ACC1, ACC2): The first committed enzyme in the pathway is acetyl-CoA carboxylase (ACC). ACC is highly regulated and is a key control point over the flux of carbon into fatty acids. ACC is a multi-enzyme complex that forms a key control point over the flux of carbon into fatty acids (Bates et al. 2013). The enzyme has multiple functions. The malonyl-CoA that is formed by the enzyme reaction is used in the plastid for fatty acid synthesis and in the cytosol in various biosynthetic pathways including fatty acid elongation, is necessary for embryo and plant development, plays a central function in embryo morphogenesis and may act as a repressor of cytokinin response. Both, *acc1-1* and *acc1-2* loss of function mutations are recessive and embryo lethal. In this abnormal embryo triacylglycerides (TAG) are synthesised at a lower concentration than in the wild-type seed. However, these TAGs are totally devoid of very long chain fatty acids (VLCFA) and consequently enriched in C18:1 (Baud et al. 2003).

A2. Malonyltransferase (MCAMT, MCAT) coding for Malonyl CoA-ACP malonyltransferase; (ACP=acyl carrier protein). The substrate of MCAMT is malonyl-CoA, and through the reaction **malonyl-ACP** is formed. MCAMT is expressed in developing seeds. Another name of the gene is EMBRYO DEFECTIVE 3147 (EMB3147). Loss of function mutants are embryo lethal at the globular stage. Overexpression of the gene in seeds leads to increased seed oil content. Taken together, MCAMT is essential for Arabidopsis cell division and is a promising target point for enhancing storage oil content in oilseed crops (Jung et al. 2019).

A3. Fatty acid synthase (FAS) is a multiprotein complex that is responsible for chain elongation up to C18 (stearate). It is a cyclic process and in each cycle two-carbon (C2) units are added to the chain. The first condensation of two acetyl groups is mediated by **KASIII** (β -ketoacyl-ACP synthase III). In a subsequent reaction chain two-carbon units are added. The 4-carbon fatty acid produced is condensed by **KASI** (β -ketoacyl-ACP synthase I) that acts to elongate 4- to 14- carbon chains. **KASII** is mainly responsible for the production of C18 chain length and controls the ratio of 16C/18C in the final products of the FAS cycles which are C16 palmitic acid and C18 stearic acid.

A4. Acyl activating enzymes (AAEs). Carboxyl-CoA ligases and related proteins are forming a large gene family, collectively called acyl activating enzymes (AAEs). Free fatty acids are relatively

chemically inert, and activation of free fatty acids to their reactive coenzyme A (CoA) derivatives is essential. AAEs are needed to activate coenzyme A (as a cofactor or linked to particular substrates). In fatty acid synthesis several members of this large gene-family are involved. These include **AAE15 and AAE16** which are probably involved in the activation of fatty acids. This occurs prior to the fatty acid elongation (via FAS) to chain lengths of 16- and 18-carbon fatty acids. Furthermore the AAE gene family includes several long-chain acyl-CoA synthetase (**LACS**; **LACS6,7,8,9**) that are involved in transport over membranes and oxidative degradation of fatty acids. **LACS9** is associated with plastid membranes and most likely involved in the *de novo* fatty acid biosynthesis pathway in the chloroplasts. LACS8 is 78% similar to LACS9 but is targeted to the ER membrane. A double mutation of *lacs8* and *lacs9* however did not affect the supply of acyl-CoAs used for TAG synthesis (Shockey and Browse, 2011).

A5. $\Delta 9$ stearoyl-ACP desaturase (SAD). The main products of *de novo* fatty acid synthesis, palmitoyl-ACP and stearoyl-ACP can be desaturated in different cellular compartments to linoleic and α -linolenic acids. The first desaturation takes place in the plastid by the action of the $\Delta 9$ stearoyl-ACP desaturase (SAD), which produces oleoyl-ACP, using ferredoxin as electron donor (Hernández et al. 2019). Therefore, SAD plays an essential role in determining the overall content of unsaturated fatty acids. In Arabidopsis locus AT2G43710 encodes a stearoyl-ACP desaturase, involved in fatty acid desaturation. Mutants with non-functional *ssi2* have increased 18:0 and reduced 18:1 fatty acids. The altered 18:1 fatty acid content in the *ssi2* mutants has an impact on SA- and JA-mediated defense.

A6. Fatty acyl-ACP thioesterases, plastidial (FATA, FATB, ALT1-4). The FAS reaction is terminated by a thioesterase mediated hydrolysis reaction. In this step the acyl carrier protein (ACP)-group of the products of fatty acid synthesis is cleaved off thereby releasing the free C16:0 and C18:0 fatty acids. In Arabidopsis, several fatty acyl-ACP thioesterases are expressed. Among them two main types can be recognized FATAs (1 and 2) and FATBs that are highly conserved, chain-length-specific and localized in the plastids. FATAs have a preference for C18:1-ACP substrates whereas FATB has a high preference for C16:0-ACP. These reactions also determines the chain length ration (C16 palmitic acid:C18 stearic acid). A *fata1 fata2* double mutant has a particular deficiency in 18:1 and 18:2 fatty acids in the seed oil whereas the *fatb* knockout has dwarf phenotype and reduction of saturated fatty acids. Furthermore, in Arabidopsis a distinct family of fatty acyl-ACP thioesterases is present, the ACYL-LIPID THIOESTERASE (ALT) gene family, that acts more on the shorter intermediates from FAS with chain lengths from C12–C16 (Pulsifer et al. 2014).

B. Key genes in transport of free fatty acids to the cytoplasm

After their synthesis in the chloroplast the majority of the the long chain fatty acids C16-C18 free fatty acids are transported to the cytoplasm, and taken up in the **cytoplasmic acyl-CoA pool**. Thereafter, further elongation, modification, acyl editing, oil and lipid assembly takes place in the ER. This requires FA and lipid transport across membranes. Several enzymes that are presumably involved in the transport process (reviewed by Li et al. 2016)

B1. FATTY ACID EXPORT 1 (FAX1; AT3G57280.1) This gene mediates the export of *de novo* synthesized FAs from chloroplast and loss of function of FAX1 impairs male fertility. Furthermore, the cuticular layer of stems from *fax1* knockouts was specifically reduced in C29-ketone waxes. FAX1 overexpressing lines showed a pronounced rise of TAGs in flowers and leaves of arabidopsis (Zhu et al. 2020)

B2. Long-chain acyl-CoA synthetases (LACsSs) Acyl activating enzyme (see above, A4)

B3. Acyl-CoA-binding proteins (ACBPs) are proposed candidate genes for engineering to enhance seed oil composition (Guo et al. 2019). Acyl-CoA binding proteins (ACBPs) harbour a conserved acyl-CoA-binding domain which enabling the binding to acyl-CoA esters. In Arabidopsis, six ACBP proteins

with acyl-CoA binding domains exist. AtACBP4, AtACBP5, and AtACBP6 were shown to play a role in determining seed oil content. They are expressed in all plant organs and are involved in fatty acid transport.

B4. Trigalactosyldiacylglycerols (TGD1-5). These genes are involved in lipid transfer from the ER to the chloroplast.

B5. ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporters: plant ABC transporter ATPases constitute a large membrane-protein family with at least 130 members in Arabidopsis and belong to the ABC Superfamily. Proteins in the A, D, and G subfamilies in animals and plants are predominantly involved in transport of lipophilic molecules.

B6. Plant non-specific lipid-transfer proteins (LTPs): transfer phospholipids as well as galactolipids across membranes. May play a role in wax or cutin deposition in the cell walls of expanding epidermal cells and certain secretory tissues.

C. Fatty acid fluxes towards storage lipids in oil bodies.

The *de novo* synthesized fatty acids that are exported from the chloroplast and activated to acyl-CoA pool in the cytoplasm. A constant exchange takes place between membrane bound fatty acids (FA-PC) and the FA in the cytoplasmic acyl-CoA pool. This process is termed "acyl-editing" and involves enzymes of the so called "Lands cycle" and "LPLAT cycle". Through acyl editing, newly synthesized 18:1 can be incorporated into membranes (FA-PC) for desaturation and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) can be released from PC to the activated fatty acids in the cytoplasmic acyl-CoA pool to end up in TAG via the "Kennedy pathway". Fatty acids in the membrane can also directly be fluxed to TAG via a conversion of PC to DAG ("PC headgroup exchange") (for details: Bates et al. 2012, Mapelli-Brahm et al. 2020, Klińska et al. 2020)

Exchange between the pool of free FAs and membrane bound FAs: "acyl editing".

In the "Lands cycle" membrane phospholipids (FA-PC) are de-acylated by phospholipases to generate lyso-phospholipids (LPCs) and free fatty acids (FA) or acyl-CoAs in the cytosol. This step is followed by re-acylation of the formed lyso-phospholipids by LPLAT type enzymes. The same process of acyl editing can also be performed in a single, reversible enzyme reaction catalysed by LPLAT type enzymes.

C1. Phospholipases, phospholipase A2 (PLA2). De-acylation of phospholipids (PC) in the "Lands cycle"

C2. Members of the LPLAT family of genes:

C2a. acyl-CoA:lysophospholipids acyltransferases (LPLATs). Involved in de-acylation of phosphatidylcholine (PC) and re-acylation of lyso-phospholipids (LPC)

C2b. acyl-CoA:lysophosphatidylcholine acyltransferases (LPCATs). Acyl editing of PC (especially sn-2 position)

C2c. Acyl-CoA:lysophosphatidylethanolamine acyltransferases (LPEAT). Acyl editing of phosphatidylethanolamine (PE)

C2d. acyl-CoA:lyso-phosphatidic acid acyltransferases (LPAAT). Acyl editing of phosphatidic acid (PA)

Free FA flux towards TAG: "Kennedy pathway"

The FAs in the cytoplasmic acyl-CoA pool are fluxed towards the Triacylglycerols (TAGs) via the "Kennedy pathway". The primary substrates of "Kennedy pathway" are cytoplasmic acyl-CoAs and (sn)-glycerol-3-phosphate (G3P). In the Kennedy pathway a stepwise acylation of G3P takes place.

C3. acyl-CoA:sn-glycerol-3-phosphate acyltransferase (GPAT), first acylation of glycerol-3-phosphate (G3P) to form lysophosphatidic acid (LPA)

C4. acyl-CoA lysophosphatidic acid acyltransferase (LPAAT), second acylation, leading to the formation of phosphatidic acid (PA).

C5. Phosphatidic acid phosphatase (PAP) subsequently de-phosphorylates phosphatidic acid (PA) to generate diacylglycerol (DAG).

Membrane bound FA (FA-PC) to DAG interconversion: "PC headgroup exchange"

Membrane bound fatty acids (FA-PC) can flux also directly to TAGs via PC to DAG conversion

C6. phosphatidylcholine:diacylglycerol cholinephosphotransferase (PDCT, ROD1). The main enzyme involved in PC headgroup exchange. This enzyme converts the PC with unsaturated FA into DAG destined to TAG. (PC-headgroup exchange). The REDUCED OLEATE DESATURATION1 (ROD1) gene (At3g15820) encoding PDCT in Arabidopsis is responsible for about 40% of the flux of PUFA from PC through DAG into TAG synthesis. It is a major reaction for the transfer of 18:1 into PC for desaturation and also for the reverse transfer of 18:2 and 18:3 into the TAG synthesis pathway (Lu et al. 2009).

C7. reversible aminoalcoholphosphotransferase (AAPT) converting PC to DAG

C8. cytidine-5'-diphosphocholine:diacylglycerol cholinephosphotransferase (CPT) converting PC to DAG

From DAG to TAG

C9. diacylglycerol acyltransferase (DGAT): acyl-CoA-dependent acylation of DAG at the sn-3 position to produce triacylglycerol (TAG). Diacylglycerol O-acyltransferase 1 (DGAT1, TAG1) is a major enzyme for oil accumulation in seeds.

C10. phospholipid:diacylglycerol acyltransferase (PDAT1) transfers membrane bound FAs (FA-PC) to DAG to form TAG. It has complementary functions with DGAT. Both are essential for triacylglycerol synthesis and normal development of both seeds and pollen.

D. Key genes in unsaturated fatty acids

The major unsaturated fatty acids in plants are oleic (18:1), linoleic (18:2), and α -linolenic (18:3) acids. The biosynthesis of the polyunsaturated fatty acids, PUFA's (C18:2 and C18:3) is coupled to the fatty acids in membrane glycerolipids of respectively the ER and the plastids, the former termed "eukaryotic pathway" the latter the "prokaryotic pathway" (He et al. 2020).

D1. FATTY ACID DESATURASE 6 (FAD6): processing 18:1(Δ 9) into 18:2(Δ 9, 12) in the plastid

D2. FATTY ACID DESATURASE 7 and 8 (FAD7 & FAD8): processing 18:2(Δ 9, 12) into 18:3(Δ 9, 12, 15) in the plastid

D3 FATTY ACID DESATURASE 2 (FAD2): Major enzyme responsible for the synthesis of 18:2 fatty acids in the ER

D4. FATTY ACID DESATURASE 3 (FAD3): is processing 18:2(Δ 9, 12) into 18:3(Δ 9, 12, 15) in the ER

D5. FATTY ACID DESATURASE 4 (FAD4): Encodes an unusual palmitate (C16:0) desaturase that is highly substrate specific.

E. Key genes in very long chain fatty acid (VLCFA) biosynthesis

Biosynthesis of very long chain fatty acids begins with the elongation of saturated and monounsaturated C16 and C18 fatty acids, that activated as acyl-CoAs by long-chain acyl-CoA synthetases (in the cytosol). The long-chain acyl-CoAs are then further elongated through FAE complexes in the ER until various chain lengths ranging from C20 up to C38 or more are reached.

E1. 3-ketoacyl-CoA synthase gene (FAE1/KCS): contributes to fatty acids elongation. Active on both saturated and mono-unsaturated acyl-CoAs of 16 and 18 carbons. Required for the elongation of C18 to C20 and of C20 to C22 fatty acids. Mediates also the synthesis of VLCFAs from 20 to 26 carbons in

length. Has no activity with polyunsaturated C18:2 and C18:3 or with acyl-CoAs having 22 carbons or longer chain length.

E2. BETA-KETOACYL REDUCTASE (KCR1, KCR2): required for the elongation of fatty acids precursors of sphingolipids, triacylglycerols, cuticular waxes and suberin.

E3. Protein-tyrosine phosphatase-like (PAS2, PTPLA). Plants with reduced expression of PAS2 show impaired embryo and seedling development.

E4. enoyl-CoA reductase (CER10) involved in very long chain fatty acids elongation reactions that are required for cuticular wax, storage lipid and sphingolipid metabolism. Mutants in this gene show abnormal organ morphology and stem glossiness.

F. Transcription factors

The oil biosynthesis pathway is regulated by a series of transcription factors, for instance **WRINKLED1** (WRI1). *wri1* mutants in *Arabidopsis* dramatically reduced in seed oil content (80% reduction) and show a wrinkled appearance. Other important transcription factors in oil biosynthesis are **ABSCISIC ACID INSENSITIVE 3** (ABI3) and the factors of the leafy cotyledon (LEC) complex. Furthermore there are other factors that regulate the pathway flux by repressing the master regulators. A list of transcription factors involved is presented in the database.

References

- Bates PD and Browse J (2012) The significance of different diacylglycerol synthesis pathways on plant oil composition and bioengineering. *Frontiers Plant Sci* 3:147. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2012.00147>
- Bates PD, Stymne S, Ohlrogge J (2013) Biochemical pathways in seed oil synthesis. *Curr. Opin Plant Biol* 16:358-364 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pbi.2013.02.015>
- Baud S, Guyon V, Kronenberger J, et al. (2003) Multifunctional acetyl-CoA carboxylase 1 is essential for very long chain fatty acid elongation and embryo development in *Arabidopsis*. *Plant J* 33(1):75-86. [10.1046/j.1365313x.2003.016010.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365313x.2003.016010.x)
- Guo Z-H, Ye Z-W, Haslam RP, Michaelson LV, Napier JA, Chye M-L (2019) *Arabidopsis* cytosolic acyl-CoA-binding proteins function in determining seed oil composition. *Plant Direct* 3:1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pld3.182>
- He M, Qin C-X, Wang X and Ding N-Z (2020) Plant Unsaturated Fatty Acids: Biosynthesis and Regulation. *Front. Plant Sci.* 11:390. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.00390>
- Hernández ML, Sicardo MD, Alfonso M, Martínez-Rivas JM (2019) Transcriptional Regulation of Stearoyl-Acyl Carrier Protein Desaturase Genes in Response to Abiotic Stresses Leads to Changes in the Unsaturated Fatty Acids Composition of Olive Mesocarp.
- Jung SH, Kim RJ, Kim KJ, Lee DH, Suh MC (2019) Plastidial and Mitochondrial Malonyl CoA-ACP Malonyltransferase is Essential for Cell Division and Its Overexpression Increases Storage Oil Content. *Plant Cell Physiol.* 60: 1239- 1249. DOI: [10.1093/pcp/pcz032](https://doi.org/10.1093/pcp/pcz032)
- Klińska S, Jasieniecka-Gazarkiewicz K, Banaś A (2019) Acyl-CoA:lysophosphatidylcholine acyltransferases (LPCATs) of *Camelina sativa* seeds: biochemical properties and function. *Planta* 250:1655-1670. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00425-019-03248-6>
- Li N, Xu C, Li-Beisson Y, Philippar (2016) Fatty Acid and Lipid Transport in Plant Cells. *Trends Plant Sci* 21:145-158 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2015.10.011>
- Li-Beisson Y, Shorosh B, Beisson F, et al. (2013) Acyl-Lipid Metabolism. *Arabidopsis Book*. 2013; 11: e0161. [10.1199/tab.0161](https://doi.org/10.1199/tab.0161)
- Lu C, Xin Z, Ren Z, Miquel M, Browse J (2009) An enzyme regulating triacylglycerol composition is encoded by the ROD1 gene of *Arabidopsis*. *PNAS* 106:18837-18842. www.pnas.org/cgi/doi/10.1073/pnas.0908848106

12. Mapelli-Brahm A, Sánchez R, Pan X, Moreno-Pérez AJ, Garcés R, Martínez-Force E, Weselake RJ, Salas JJ and Venegas-Calderón M (2020) Functional Characterization of Lysophosphatidylcholine: Acyl-CoA Acyltransferase Genes From Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.). *Front. Plant Sci.* 11:403. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.00403>
13. Pulsifer IP, Lowe C, Narayanan SA, Busuttill AS, et al. (2014) Acyl-lipid thioesterase1–4 from *Arabidopsis thaliana* form a novel family of fatty acyl–acyl carrier protein thioesterases with divergent expression patterns and substrate specificities *Plant Mol Biol* 84:549-563. [10.1007/s11103-013-0151-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11103-013-0151-z)
14. Shockley J and Browse J (2011). Genome-level and biochemical diversity of the acyl-activating enzyme superfamily in plants. *Plant J* 66:143-60. [10.1111/j.1365-3113.2011.04512.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3113.2011.04512.x)
15. Yuan L and Li R (2020) Metabolic Engineering a Model Oilseed *Camelina sativa* for the Sustainable Production of High-Value Designed Oils. *Front. Plant Sci.*, 12 February 2020. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.00011>
16. Zhu L, He S, Liu Y, et al. (2020) *Arabidopsis* FAX1 mediated fatty acid export is required for the transcriptional regulation of anther development and pollen wall formation. *Plant Mol Biol* 104:187-201. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11103-020-01036-5>.